

STHITPRAGYA: A STEP FORWARD TO EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

Indian scriptures are very famous across the globe for their wide diversity of knowledge and wisdom. These scriptures are enlightening for Indians as well as people across the world. One such prominently known ancient scripture, Bhagavad-Gita is widely researched by scholars all over the world. Different disciplines such as Philosophy, Psychology, and Management found this text incredibly knowledgeable and significant. The present study attempts to explore the teachings of Bhagavad-Gita, especially the understanding of the concept Sthitpragya as mentioned in chapter II of this epic. Various Scholars who studied this concept earlier had drawn a parallel concept of emotional intelligence. While Sthitpragya and emotional intelligence both possess a few similarities, there are substantial differences. This paper uniquely represents how these two concepts Sthitpragya and emotional intelligence are similar and distinct from each other. What it means to be emotionally intelligent and how it is different from being Sthitpragya has been extensively discussed in the light of Bhagavad-Gita. The findings of this review will be helpful to strengthen the understanding of the Indian concept of Sthitpragya. Sthitpragya is very useful for an individual to balance different aspects of his life and become a fully functioning individual. This study identifies a need of empirical exploration for a proper understanding of this concept.

Keywords: Sthitpragya, Emotional Intelligence, Bhagavad-Gita, Self-management, Fully-functioning Individual

Introduction

आनोभद्राःऋतवोयन्तुविश्वतः।

Let noble thoughts come to us from every side (Rigveda, 1-89-i).

This verse from one of the oldest Veda recites that we should accept and respect the knowledge from every side without having any doubt about its origin. India is one of the oldest civilisations in the world and has a tradition of knowledge which can be still found in its countless scriptures. Ancient Indian scriptures has been accepted as a vast source of wisdom by numerous scholars from the distinct parts of the world. These scriptures consist of teachings for various aspect of human life. Not only Indian but people across the globe can find these insights relevant and applicable in diverse dimensions of their life. Four Vedas namely, Rigveda, Samaveda, Yajurveda, and Atharvaveda are prominent Indian scriptures. Along with the four Vedas we have Ramayana, Mahabharata, Shrimad Bhagavad-Gita, Arthashastra, Vidurneeti and

108 Upanishads. In addition to four Vedas, Bhagavad-Gita considered to be the fifth Veda (the essence of the four Vedas) (Easwaran, 1985; Robinson, 2005). Present study is based on the insights and teachings of these scriptures and attempts to explore the concept of Sthitpragya derived originally from Bhagavad-Gita. The understanding of Sthitpragya is deeply inherited in yoga practices and Indian philosophy. This concept was introduced in Bhagavad-Gita by Lord Shri Krishna while giving Arjuna a broad understanding of his on-going conflicts and the true nature of reality. Before taking a deep consideration of Sthitpragya, a brief discussion of the circumstances in which Lord Shri Krishna gave this knowledge to Arjuna is needed.

Bhagavad-Gita as the name suggests is popularly known as the song of Gods. This is a part of the renowned epic Mahabharata. A brief description of Mahabharata will help to understand the storyline and inception of the term Sthitpragya. In ancient India, a huge kingdom named Hastinapur was established

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by the ancestors of Kuruvanshies. In Later generations, Maharaj Dhritarashtra's and his younger brother Pandu's sons started to compete with each other to rule the kingdom. These circumstances led to the greatest warfare ever in India among the Sons of Dhritarashtra (Kauravas) and Sons of Pandu (Pandavas). Armies of both parties were gathered in the field of Kurukshetra and war was about to begin. At this moment Arjuna became emotional and said to Lord Shri Krishna that how can he kill his kith and kin, isn't it a horrible act? The attachment with his kins made Arjuna unable to hold the weapons. After hearing him patiently, Lord Shri Krishna addressed Arjuna and gave an account of the true nature of reality including the body and the soul. Again, Lord Shri Krishna talked about the Kshatriya dharma (duty of a warrior) and karma-yoga. Then a lot of aspects related to human life had been discussed in a form of dialogue between the two. The preach of Lord Shri Krishna led to the composition of the Bhagavad Gita into 18 chapters each providing an understanding of distinct subjects. In chapter II of Bhagavad-Gita, Arjuna puts his anguish into such utterances that how could he engage in battle with those who are worthy of worship (Pitamah Bhishma and Guru Drona)? After executing all the near and dear ones of the family how could he overcome these mighty losses? Arjuna, as a disciple, requests Lord Shri Krishna to guide him because he is totally confused about his duty. Listening to Arjuna's state of upheaval and being unwilling to perform his duty, Lord Shri Krishna commenced his message by following verses (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 11 & 15)-

अशोच्यानन्वशोचस्त्वं प्रजावादांश्च भाषसे ।

गतासूनगतासंश्च नानुशोचन्ति पण्डिताः ॥ 11॥

The Blessed Lord said: For those that should not be grieved for, you have grieved; yet you speak words of wisdom. For the dead and for the living, the wise never grieve.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

As Arjuna was able to understand his ongoing emotional state and comprehend it in reasonable words, Lord Shri Krishna praised him for that and advised him to be wise and not to grieve. Then in the next few verses, Lord Shri Krishna addressed the nature of reality and how it comprises the body and the soul. One who realizes this, stands the same in pain and pleasure.

यं हि न व्यथयन्त्येते पुरुषं पुरुषर्षभ।

समदुःखसुखं धीरं सोऽमृतत्वाय कल्पते॥15॥

[Whom surely these afflict not, such a man, a "Bull among men", is firm and faces equally both pain & pleasure. He alone is fit for realizing the Immortality of the Self] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Lord Shri Krishna advised Arjuna not to worry about the things that are meant to demolish (body) and the one which is inevitable and cannot be destroyed (soul or Atma). He emphasized in the following verse (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 31) that Arjuna must understand and perform his duty as a warrior -

स्वधर्ममपि चावेक्ष्य न विकम्पितुमर्हसि ।

धर्म्याद्धि युद्धाच्छ्रेयोऽन्यत्क्षत्रियस्य न विद्यते ॥ 31॥

[Further, looking at your own duty, you ought not to waver; for, indeed, higher than a righteous war, there is nothing other for a Kshatriya.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Answering Arjuna's doubt about killing his kins, Lord Shri Krishna in the following verses (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 38) told him to perform his duty as a warrior without having any single thought of good or bad, gain or loss, misery or enjoyment-

सुखदुःखे समे कृत्वा लाभालाभौ जयाजयौ ।

ततो युद्धाय युज्यस्व नैवं पापमवाप्स्यसि ॥ 38॥

[Keeping your balance of mind in pleasure and pain, in gain and loss, and in victory or defeat, engage yourself in battle for battle's sake, thus you shall incur no sin.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

One must perform his duty and obligations for the sake of duty itself not for the results attached to it. Giving an account of profound thoughts underlying performing one's duty without longing for the results, Lord Shri Krishna preached the following very well-known verses (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 47)-

कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्ते मा फलेषु कदाचन ।

मा कर्मफलहेतुर्भूर्मा ते सङ्गोऽस्त्वकर्मणि ॥ 47 ॥

[Thy right is to work only, not to be concerned with its fruits; let not the fruits of actions be your motive, nor should you be attached to inaction (laziness.)] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

While involving in action one should always pour his attention to work itself. No work should be performed having thought of its result in mind. Again, this detachment from the results of work should not lead to the state of inaction. One must act and complete his obligations while detaching themselves from the greed of outcomes.

While interpreting the fundamentals of yoga, Lord Shri Krishna stated that (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 48)

कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्ते मा फलेषु कदाचन ।

मा कर्मफलहेतुर्भूर्मा ते सङ्गोऽस्त्वकर्मणि ॥ 47 ॥

[Be steadfast in Yoga by performing actions without attachment, O Dhananjaya; Become balanced in success and failure. Evenness of mind is called Yoga.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

In simple words, performing own duty and actions without having attachment of results and remain the same in victory or defeat, this equanimity is called Yoga. In the next few verses, Lord Shri Krishna approves that yoga enables one to detach himself from selfish goals and follow one's duty with non-attachment. This is the best path to liberation from all worldly sufferings. Once intellect crosses the longings and attachments to worldly desires then one itself attains indifference and

complete union with self or ultimate reality.

After listening to the unique impact of karma-yoga on one's being, Arjuna inquired about the qualities of a man with steady wisdom in the following verses (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 54)-

स्थितप्रज्ञस्य का भाषा समाधिस्थस्य केशव ।

स्थितधीः किं प्रभाषेत किमासीत ब्रजेत किम् ॥ 54॥

[Arjuna said: Describe to me the man of steady wisdom, who is in the Superconscious State, O Keshava (Lord Shri Krishna)? How does the one of steady wisdom speak? How does he sit? How does he walk?] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Lord Shri Krishna already gave Arjuna a brief knowledge about the body, the soul, and the true nature of reality till now. He also comprehended to Arjuna the importance of performing one's duty in any circumstances without any attachment (Karma-yoga). After listening to Arjuna's inquiry about Sthitpragya, Lord Shri Krishna started to illustrate him the virtues of Sthitpragya. Lord Shri Krishna refers Sthitpragya (the emotionally stable person) is one who remains unperturbed in the face of calamity, and takes good or evil with equanimity. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 55)

प्रजहाति यदा कामान्सर्वान्पार्थ मनोगतान् ।

आत्मन्येवात्मना तुष्टः स्थितप्रज्ञस्तदोच्यते ॥ 55॥

[DESIRE - when a man casts off all of it from his mind, O Partha (Arjuna), and lives satisfied in his Self, by his Self, then he is said to be one of steady wisdom.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Qualities of Sthitpragya as told by Lord Shri Krishna are mentioned in Bhagavad-Gita from shlokas 55 to 58 of chapter II, as given below-

He is neither cheerful when something good happens, nor is he affected when things go against him. Simply he remains detached from both occurrences, pain, and pleasure.

He who has no fear in his mind and free from all the attachments called Sthitpragya. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 56)

दुःखेष्वनुद्विग्नमनाः सुखेषु विगतस्पृहः ।

वीतरागभयक्रोधः स्थितधीर्मुनिरुच्यते ॥ 56॥

[In adversity, his mind remains unshaken; In pleasure, it remains without hankering; Free from attachment, fear, and anger - such a man is called a "Sage of Steady Wisdom"]. (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

? This does not mean that he lacks sensitivity. He can keep his emotions in check and master the skill of withdrawing his feelings away from the matter of enjoyment or distress. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 57)

यः सर्वत्रानभिस्नेहस्तत्तत्प्राप्य शुभाशुभम् ।

नाभिनन्दति न द्वेष्टि तस्य प्रजा प्रतिष्ठिता ॥ 57॥

[He who is everywhere without Attachment; on meeting with anything good or bad; who neither rejoices nor hates; his wisdom is said to be fixed (steady)]. (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

As a tortoise withdraws its head and legs inside the protective cover of its shell whenever it faces danger, so does an emotionally stable person. He withdraws all his emotions and feelings within himself and remains unperturbed. He has the power to emotionally attach or detach from any situation, at his will. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 58)

यदा संहरते चायं कूर्मोऽङ्गानीव सर्वशः ।

इन्द्रियाणीन्द्रियार्थभ्यस्तस्य प्रजा प्रतिष्ठिता ॥ 58॥

[When a man Withdraws, as a tortoise does its limbs from all sides, his senses from the sense-objects, then his wisdom becomes steady]. (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada).

As we see, in Bhagavad-Gita, Lord Shri Krishna takes a more comprehensive view of the problem related to emotional turmoil which anyone can face someplace in his life. He points out the causes, discusses the effect, and also offers the means of encoun-

tering the problems successfully. And as a conclusion of all emotional distress, he identifies the qualities of an emotionally stable person and completes the whole view of problems and solutions.

Lord Shri Krishna added that how one can persist as Sthitpragya; that one should withdraw his senses from worldly attachments and dwell them into the true nature of reality or supreme being. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shloka 61)

तानि सर्वाणि संयम्य युक्त आसीत मत्परः ।

वशे हि यस्येन्द्रियाणि तस्य प्रजा प्रतिष्ठिता ॥ 61॥

[Having restrained them all (the senses), he should sit steadfast, intent on Me; he whose senses are under control, his wisdom is said to be steady.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Tracing the root cause of all emotional turmoil, Lord Shri Krishna identifies desire and anger as the two fundamental reasons that lead an individual to his downfall. This has been described in the following verses very beautifully. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shlokas 62&63)

ध्यायतो विषयान्पुंसः सङ्गस्तेषूपजायते ।

सङ्गात्सञ्जायते कामः कामात्क्रोधोऽभिजायते ॥ 62॥

[When a man thinks of objects attachment for them arises; from attachment, desire is born; from desire arises anger] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

क्रोधाद्भवति सम्मोहः सम्मोहात्स्मृतिविभ्रमः ।

स्मृतिभ्रंशाद् बुद्धिनाशो बुद्धिनाशात्प्रणश्यति ॥ 63॥

[From anger comes delusion; from delusion comes the loss of memory; from loss of memory, destruction of discrimination; from the destruction of discrimination, he Perishes.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada).

It is the strong desire for and attachment to worldly objects that drive an individual to his downfall. Desire when not satisfied leads to anger, which in turn leads to delusion. This further destroys the ability to discriminate be-

tween right and wrong, which leads to complete ruin.

But once a person attained the state of Sthitpragya, he or she becomes calm in various worldly situations. Or in other words, his mind cannot be contaminated by worldly distractions. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shlokas 64)

रागद्वेषवियुक्तैस्तु विषयानिन्द्रियैश्चरन् ।

आत्मवश्यैर्विधेयात्मा प्रसादमधिगच्छति ॥ 64॥

[But, free from attraction and repulsion, moving among the objects with senses under self-restraint, the self-controlled one most certainly attains the 'Prize' of peace.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

After being Sthitpragya, a person attains the peace and contentment that continuously help him to maintain his tranquillity and steadiness of mind. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shlokas 65)

प्रसादे सर्वदुःखानां हानिरस्योपजायते ।

प्रसन्नचेतसो ह्याशु बुद्धिः पर्यवतिष्ठते ॥ 65॥

[In that 'Prize', all pains of his get destroyed as they arise; because of his Tranquil Mind (the Prize), soon his intellect becomes steady.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

Being Sthitpragya is a necessary condition for other activities that are helpful for the holistic development of an individual. It helps in mindfulness, meditation, attaining the knowledge of one's self, and the serenity of mind. (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shlokas 65)

नास्ति बुद्धिरयुक्तस्य न चायुक्तस्य भावना ।

न चाभावयतः शान्तिरशान्तस्य कुतः सुखम् ॥ 66॥

[There is no knowledge of the Self to the unsteady; and to the unsteady, no meditation is possible; and to the unmeditative, there is no PEACE; to the one with no peace, whence is Happiness?] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

The ultimate goal of being Sthitpragya is to understand the true nature of reality, leaving all the worldliness behind, and attaining oneness with the true nature of the reality or Brah-

man. As mentioned in following verses (Bhagavad-Gita, Ch. II, Shlokas 71 & 72)

विहाय कामान्यः सर्वान्पुमांश्चरति निःस्पृहः ।

निर्ममो निरहङ्कारः स शान्तिमधिगच्छति ॥ 71॥

[He who abandons all desires, and moves about without any longing, devoid of 'mine'-ness and 'I'-ness (ego), he attains the Supreme Peace] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

एषा ब्राह्मी स्थितिः पार्थ नैनां प्राप्य विमुह्यति ।

स्थित्वास्यामन्तकालेऽपि ब्रह्मनिर्वाणमृच्छति ॥ 72॥

[This is the Brahmic State, O Son of Pritha (Arjuna). Attaining this, none is deluded. Established therein, even at the end of life, one attains oneness with Brahman.] (Translated by Swami Gurubhaktananada)

In essence, the above-discussed verses denote that if one has the desire for worldly gratifications and if it is not fulfilling it will lead to rage and anger. Thus, desires and anger are two primary reasons that can cause a state of emotional chaos in any person's life. Unsatisfied desires are key to rage which in turn lead to delusion. One lost control over his senses and failed to discern between right and wrong. This delusional state results in complete ruin in life. Here the privileges appear of being a Sthitpragya. As discussed above, a Sthitpragya withdraws himself from the results of his actions and he executes his duties for the sake of duty itself. He does not possess the desire for worldly enjoyment. Therefore, he remains calm during different emotional-provoking situations occurring in everyday life. This aids him to avoid lots of daily hassles. The tranquillity of his mind in turn facilitates him in meditative and other essential activities to realize the self and attain the oneness with ultimate reality. That is what the ultimate goal of a person's life is to be one with supreme reality. Thus, being a Sthitpragya not only avoids the daily annoyances but helps one to achieve the ultimate goal of his life.

There are many misconceptions related to this concept. Often it had been misunderstood as similar or parallel to being emotionally intelligent. A very brief description of emotional intelligent and how being Sthitpragya is completely distinct from being emotionally intelligent has been discussed in the present study. Before looking upon the differences and similarity between two, understanding of what is emotional intelligence is needed.

Emotional intelligence (EI) has been discovered as a result of series of studies undertaken by researchers and psychologists with an attempt to understand why people with high intellectual abilities are unsuccessful in life. According to Salovey and Mayer (1990), "A form of intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions". This was the initial definition given by Peter Salovey and John Mayer, who originally used the term emotional intelligence in their published writing. Later on, they revised their definition of emotional intelligence as: "The ability to perceive emotion, integrate emotion to facilitate thought, understand emotions, and to regulate emotions to promote personal growth" (Mayer and Salovey, 1997). A clearer definition of EI was "It is the ability to sense, understand and effectively apply the power and acumen of emotions as a source of human energy, creativity, innovation, cooperation, communication, collaboration, information and influence" (Cooper and Sawaf, 1997). Term emotional intelligence gain more popularity after Daniel Goleman (1995) published a book named "Emotional Intelligence: Why It can Matter More than IQ". According to Goleman (1998) "Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships" Goleman (1998) recognized four core competencies of EI in competency Model: Self- awareness,

Self-management, Social-awareness, Relationship-management.

Hence, the concept of emotional intelligence predominantly deals with the following areas:

- The ability to understand and express one's own emotions constructively.
- The ability to understand other's feelings and maintain healthy interpersonal relationships.
- The ability to manage and regulate emotions of oneself and others in an effective manner.
- The ability to cope credibly with novel circumstances and solve problems of a personal and interpersonal nature by using emotions positively, and
- The ability to be appropriately optimistic, positive and self-motivated in setting and achieving goals.

EI can be simply understood as smartly dealing with the emotions in life. One's capability of having and understanding related emotions in distinct contexts such as related to oneself and others is the primary skill of being emotionally intelligent. Using this awareness in such a way that can enhance the desired outcome is the second most required mastery of being emotionally intelligent. These abilities of understanding and expressing emotions rightly and sufficiently provide the advantage of maintaining adequate balance in one's interpersonal relations. Again, the potential to manage and regulate emotions helps a person to deal with plenty of emotionally unsettling situations and also benefits in problem-solving. Consequently, an individual can preserve a satisfactory equilibrium in different domains of his life while being optimistic and enthusiastic at the same time.

The above description of Sthitpragya and emotional intelligence made it clear that being Sthitpragya is completely different from being emotionally intelligent. What is being emotionally intelligent means according to Mayer and Salovey's 'ability model' (2004)?

It identified four stages through which a person becomes emotionally intelligent -

- Emotional Perception: to identifying one's emotions through his expression
- Emotional Assimilation: considering the feeling aspect while involved in other cognitive activities such as thinking, memory or judgement
- Emotional Understanding: a deep understanding of variety of emotions adding a cultural aspect in it.
- Emotional Management: managing own and others' emotions effectively that can facilitate the person into more positive and forward direction.

A Sthitpragya, according to Lord Shri Krishna, is "one who remains unperturbed in the face of calamity, and takes good or evil with equanimity". He cannot be affected by worldly situations. Whether it be a victorious occurrence or a moment full of sorrow, he endures both with the same serenity of mind. Once realizes the true nature of reality, Sthitpragya grasps that whatever pain or pleasure is related to material objects is temporary and going to devastate soon. He becomes aware of his and others' feelings and respects the emotions but never dwells on that. He withdraws all his senses from worldly attachments and maintains the steadiness of his mind in all circumstances.

Thus, as per Mayer & Salovey (2004) description of EI, it is to understand our emotion, express them appropriately, to be able to distinguish between different emotions and finally to use this emotional knowledge to think, analyse and behave rationally. On the other hand, the Bhagavad-Gita uses the word Sthitpragya in two ways. Firstly, the term is used as a noun and refers to a person, who possesses the qualities of an ideal human being. Secondly, this term is used as an adjective, to denote a state of being wise. The word Sthitpragya is a compound derived from two Sanskrit words, Sthit(?????) and Pragya(?????). Here, Sthit means 'steady' and the

word Pragya itself consists of a deeply rooted philosophical meaning. The Upanishadic reference of Pragya denotes it as 'Consciousness in its invisible form refers to pure bliss or Brahman' [????????? ?????????? ?????????? (Verse 5 of Mandukya Upanishad)]. Pragya is widely used in Vedic and Upanishadic literature as a state of knowing or consciousness that is not different from ultimate reality or true bliss or Brahman. Therefore, together Sthit and Pragya indicate 'one who has a steady consciousness'. It refers to that "one is in a constant state of knowing the true reality and has deeply internalized that". He realizes the self and is in a complete state of knowing that everything beyond Brahman is fake, only Brahman is true. This constant state of knowing becomes important for being a Sthitpragya because knowledge alone is not sufficient, one must sustain that experience of pure bliss in himself. The Bhagavad-Gita also characterizes 'Sthitpragya' as a Samadhistha(?????????), 'one who is wrapped in meditation and is established in pure consciousness. The word Samadhistha(?????????) is a compound of three Sanskrit words, sam(??), adhi(??), and stha(??). Sam means 'equal', Adhi means 'attention' and Stha denotes the 'possessive sense'. The Samadhistha can pay equal attention to both positive and negative things in the world and remain equally detached from happiness and suffering. Finally, the Gita talks about the Sthitpragya as 'Yogastha(?????????)', meaning somebody 'established in the yoga'. It suggests that the Sthitpragya not only practices yoga but also has internalized it so that all his actions are conducted with non-attachment.

As emotional intelligence mainly talks about the understanding of variety of emotions and effectively managing them to work rationally, the concept of Sthitpragya talks about emotional stability, a step forward to emotional intelligence. Being Sthitpragya consists not only a wide variety of qualities as discussed above. It also indicates that person possess a deep

understanding of not just emotions but the root cause of distinct emotions. Where emotionally intelligent person manages the emotions, Sthitpragya takes a different route to solve the problems arising from these negative emotions and use the positive emotional state with a balanced approach. Achieving a state where positive and negative emotions become the same, benefits one to act commonly in both situations, no haphazard from negative ones and no enthusiasm for positive one. This state of mind benefits to work more efficiently in different situations, well-adjust in life, and maintain a balance in different roles played by a person.

Subsequently, when emotional intelligence talks about being smart with emotions, Sthitpragya on the other hand talks about being wise with emotions. Having an openness to a wide variety of emotions but remaining in the same state of mind in all those emotional situations is a way ahead of being emotionally intelligent. This aids a person to deal effectively with various emotionally provoking situations while preserving his peacefulness of mind. This steady mind enables an individual to the fundamental state of practicing yoga and other meditative activities. Being Sthitpragya, as discussed above, is about complete understanding that the world around us is not true, it's only a mere reflection of the ultimate reality. This awareness enables a person to act wisely in different situations. He will certainly feel emotions and act according to the situation but will not engrossed in it. This steady state of being wise and residing in complete bliss makes a person more peaceful. Consequently, going beyond the perception, assimilation, understanding, and management of emotions; Sthitpragya acknowledges the root cause of arising emotions, maintains equanimity in his mind, and acts in corresponding with the situation without being affected by it. These possibilities support an individual to attain his entire strength and become a fully functioning individual.

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